

Phenology of coastal zooplankton in Skjálfandi Bay, Northern Iceland: a food web perspective

Abstract

The waters around Iceland are highly productive and biodiverse, and serve as key nearshore spawning and nursing grounds for fish, with zooplankton being a driving link in the food web. Yet, zooplankton data at relevant spatial and temporal scales from this region are lacking. We examined the influence of seasonality, water physico-chemistry and chlorophyll-*a* (chl_a; in situ and satellite observations) on zooplankton abundance and size structure, and baleen whale sightings in Skjálfandi Bay, Northern Iceland. Silicon-rich river inputs drove strong seasonal shifts in temperature, salinity, and turbidity at plume stations. Chl_a peaked in late May, followed by an in situ peak in zooplankton abundance in July that aligned with the seasonal temperature peak. Zooplankton was dominated by *Calanus* species, and nearshore (<7.5 km) communities were lower in abundance and biomass, and consisted primarily of smaller (<1.5 mm) individuals compared to offshore assemblages with higher abundance and higher proportion of larger (>1.5 mm) individuals. Blue and minke whales were present primarily early in the season before the chl_a peak, with minke whales restricted close to shore, while humpback whales peaked later during summer, and were most common in mid-bay areas with higher biomass of large *Calanus*. Overall, we found that (1) rivers drove strong seasonal shifts in water physico-chemistry in the nearshore plume stations, (2) chl_a positively influenced copepod abundance, and the latter cooccurred in time and space with humpbacks, and (3) distance from the shore and temperature were the most important abiotic drivers of the food web. Our findings highlight that coastal zones are distinct feeding habitats and ecological niches that support diverse food-web interactions.

These zones, therefore, represent functionally important habitats, and monitoring programs should include such areas, including <7.5 and 25 km from shore, to capture whole-ecosystem dynamics.

Keywords

Arctic, *Calanus*, cetaceans, food web, Iceland, marine mammals, north Atlantic, size structure.

Introduction

The Arctic and the North Atlantic Oceans harbor high biodiversity and production of marine resources that are important for the entire ecosystem, including humans that inhabit their shores (AMAP, 2024). At the same time, these regions are particularly affected by climate change that strongly impacts the food web functioning, from primary producers to large mammals (Greene et al., 2008; Pampoulie et al., 2024; Stenseth 2004). Identifying key impacts requires comprehensive studies across appropriate spatial, temporal, and ecological scales, including the phenology of seasonal processes and how they connect from local to regional scales (Flensburg et al., 2025; Fulton et al., 2004; Mannocci et al., 2017). Also, ecological scales matter: climate change-driven shifts to smaller size structure of zooplankton or fish populations influence productivity at a large scale (Heneghan et al., 2023; Ratnarajah et al., 2023). Thus, acquiring empirical data at a proper spatial, temporal, and ecological resolution will aid in developing fundamental ecological knowledge as well as in addressing future challenges that lay ahead of this important region.

The waters around Iceland are highly productive and biodiverse (Astthorsson et al., 2007; Lörz et al., 2021; Pike et al., 2019), and serve as spawning and nursing grounds for key economic and ecological fish species (Pálsson et al., 2012; Pampoulie et al., 2024). Marine mammals are an integral part of the ecosystem, with high abundance observed both nearshore and offshore (Pike et al., 2009, 2019; Víkingsson et al., 2015). Iceland has two distinct marine regimes: southern and western Icelandic waters are dominated by warmer Atlantic currents, while northern and eastern regions are influenced by colder Arctic waters, bringing episodes of lower temperatures and salinity from ice sheet melt (Astthorsson et al., 2007; Devana et al., 2021). A notable area of the

Northern Icelandic shore is Skjálfandi Bay. It is a major whale-watching site, hosting abundant and diverse populations of foraging mammals within only ~25 km from the shoreline (Charles et al., 2025; Malinauskaite et al., 2022). As commonly observed in polar systems, the food chain here is relatively simple with few links, where primary production, rather than predation, regulates the abundance of higher trophic levels: from phytoplankton through zooplankton (mostly *Calanus* copepods), krill (mostly *Meganyctiphanes norvegica* and *Thysanoessa inermis*), capelin (*Mallotus villosus*), and cod (*Gadus morhua*), extending to marine mammals (Astthorsson et al., 2007). Nonetheless, despite the relatively high *Calanus* abundance observed in northern Iceland (Astthorsson & Gislason, 1995), estimates of krill abundance in this region remains markedly low (Silva et al., 2016, 2017). Thus, *Calanus* zooplankton play a pivotal role in channeling energy, nutrients, and high-quality fatty acids from phytoplankton to fish and marine mammals (Bandara et al., 2023; Eysteinnsson et al., 2020; Müller-Navarra et al., 2000), making them the cornerstone of the food web.

Since the 1960s, The Marine and Freshwater Research Institute has conducted long-term environmental and zooplankton monitoring around Iceland that identified the large-scale patterns of zooplankton biomass and diversity (Astthorsson et al., 2007; Astthorsson & Gislason, 1995; Gislason & Silva, 2012), and revealed that their long-term trends were related to climate change and salinity anomalies driven by ice melt (Astthorsson & Gislason, 1995; Beare et al., 2000; Gislason et al., 2009; Gislason & Astthorsson, 2004; Gislason & Silva, 2012). Although this monitoring program has provided valuable insights into climate-driven changes and ocean freshening in the region, it has caveats (Gislason & Silva, 2012) that limit our knowledge of spatiotemporal patterns of nearshore zooplankton around Iceland, including Skjálfandi Bay.

First, the monitoring program was designed to capture large-scale patterns rather than fine-scale variability closer to the shore, hence Skjálfandi Bay lies outside the national monitoring program. However, this area is characterized by several features common for Icelandic coastal regions. The bay receives sediment-rich inputs from two rivers that may increase the transport of limiting minerals, such as phosphorus and iron (Eiriksdottir et al., 2015), and potentially nitrogen. Thus, riverine inputs may enhance productivity in the bay and create a gradient from river-affected nearshore to offshore (open ocean) conditions further across the bay, but this has not been studied to date. Second, the program performs sampling in late May to early June (Astthorsson & Gislason, 1995; Beare et al., 2000; Gislason et al., 2009; Gislason & Astthorsson, 2004), while zooplankton peaks between July and August (Gislason & Silva, 2012). Moreover, although Skjálfandi Bay is a place of frequent baleen whale sightings, the relationship between high abundance of marine mammals and zooplankton, and their phenology, has not been studied despite clear evidence of a link (Astthorsson et al., 2007; Pampoulie et al., 2024). Hence, empirical data of better resolution in time and space are needed to identify major drivers of the local food web, from algae to mammal filter-feeders. Only then will we be able to fully assess the nearshore ecological importance, and help prioritize monitoring efforts that deliver policy-relevant data for national-scale understanding and management objectives.

Here, we analyze the abundance and size structure of zooplankton community from April to August 2024 in Skjálfandi Bay. We further evaluate how its dynamics structure the food web, by relating zooplankton observations to chlorophyll-*a* concentration (in situ and satellite-derived), and baleen whale sightings. Specifically, we investigate: (1) the seasonal succession of phytoplankton and zooplankton, (2) the spatial variation of zooplankton assemblages from river plumes to offshore, and (3) the relationship between zooplankton and baleen whale occurrence.

Thus, we aim to provide novel insights into the ecology of zooplankton in Skjálfandi Bay, and how it links the lower and upper trophic levels over different spatial and temporal scales.

Material and methods

Study site, sampling, and water physico-chemistry

Skjálfandi Bay is located in the north of Iceland and receives sediment-rich inputs from two main rivers; glacier-fed Skjálfandaflót and Laxá draining Lake Mývatn (hereafter “skj river” and “lax river”), in addition to several smaller rivers on the western side of the bay. We established a transect comprising five stations ranging from river plumes to marine conditions: two located within plumes (Skjálfandaflót and Laxá, hereafter ‘skj plume’ and ‘lax plume’) and three marine stations (d3, d4, d5) positioned approximately 7.5 km, 13 km, and 25 km offshore from the plume areas (Fig 1A). The plume stations had maximum depth of approximately 10 m, while the marine stations d3, d4, and d5 reached depths of about 120 m, 140 m, and 180 m, respectively.

We collected water and zooplankton samples on four occasions in the bay between April and August 2024, and sampled the rivers close to the marine sampling dates. On 19 April, lax plume and marine station d3 were sampled; on 27 May and 14 August, lax plume and marine stations d3 and d5 were sampled; and on 10 July, all five stations were sampled. At every station, Secchi depth was measured, from which the light attenuation coefficient (K_d) was estimated. Water samples were taken at 1, 5, 10, 20, 30 and 50 m depth, or until reaching the bottom, using a 5L Niskin bottle. Water was collected into 5L bottles, from which temperature was measured immediately using an analogue pool-thermometer, and stored in dark and cool conditions during transport to the laboratory, where water was mixed before further measurements. For in situ

chlorophyll-*a* (chl_a), 400 mL were filtered onto GF/F filters which were stored and transported at –20 °C in dark aluminum foil envelopes. The filters were extracted in 95% ethanol overnight in darkness at 4°C and chl_a was measured with a Perkin Elmer LS 30 fluorometer (433 nm excitation and 674 nm emission wavelength). Chl_a depth profiles were vertically integrated from the surface to 50 m using trapezoidal integration to estimate areal concentrations (per m²).

Samples for salinity were frozen (–20 °C) until thorough thawing and measurement using a refractometer (each measurement verified on 2 different refractometers, calibration with milli-Q water). Frozen seawater samples were also analyzed for inorganic nutrients, including PO₄³⁻ (P) and NO_x (N), as well as silicate (Si-SO₄: Si), using a San⁺⁺ continuous flow analyzer (Skalar Analytical B.V., The Netherlands) following modified protocols of Grasshoff K et al. (1999). These were performed following accredited seawater analysis methods at the AU Ecoscience laboratory in Roskilde, Denmark. Inorganic nutrients were averaged from 1, 5, and 10 m depth.

We collected zooplankton from the entire water column using vertical net hauls of a 90 µm mesh WP2 plankton net (ø57 cm) from approximately 2 m above the seafloor at plume stations and ~10 m above the seafloor at marine stations. We chose a 90 µm mesh size instead of the 200 µm net used in the ongoing monitoring program in Northern Iceland to catch smaller, potentially important zooplankton such as copepod nauplii and protozoans. Using an automatic winch, we slowly (~1 m/s) retrieved the net and flushed it three times to recover all biomass. Samples were preserved in 300 mL dark bottles with 10 mL/L non-acidified Lugol's solution. As decomposition became evident in dense samples, additional Lugol was added later.

Spatiotemporal patterns in chlorophyll

We derived daily modelled surface chl_a concentrations for the northern coast of Iceland for March–November 2024 using per-pixel chl_a products available through open geospatial repositories accessed via Google Earth Engine. These included Sentinel-3 OLCI (variable “CHL”, 300 m) and the multi-sensor Ocean Colour CCI product (variable “chlor-a”, 4 km; Morel & Antoine, 2011; Global Ocean Colour, 2026; Copernicus Climate Change Service, 2026). We derived both daily time series of summary statistics (mean, standard deviation, and the number of valid pixels) and monthly maps of surface chl_a for the full study area. Monthly composites were generated as pixel-wise means across all available observations within each calendar month and subsequently clipped to the region of interest. OLCI was treated as the primary data source; when OLCI pixels were removed by cloud masking or other validity filters, we complemented them with CCI observations resampled onto a common 300 m grid.

Zooplankton analysis

We analyzed zooplankton using image analysis. Depending on the density of individuals, the samples were subsampled to up to a 16th using a Motoda subsampler. Then, we flushed the subsamples using a 70 µm meshed sieve to remove Lugol, and re-suspended the zooplankton in artificial seawater (salinity ~34) and scanned (photographed) one subsample per sample using the ZooSCAN (Hydroptic) instrument. We did this by pouring condensed, subsampled zooplankton into a rectangular plastic chamber (~25×15 cm), scanning the entire chamber surface using VueScan (version 9.7.67), and analyzing each picture using the ImageJ (version 1.54g). We counted all zooplankton in the pictures and identified them into three categories: copepods (copepodite and adult stages together), nauplii, and other (i.e., crab larvae, krill, worm-shaped animals, unidentified animals). Although we have not formally identified zooplankton to any finer taxonomic level, we observed that adult copepods consisted primarily of the genus *Calanus*.

The proportion of other animals was 0% for the majority of samples, and never exceeded 4.2% (see raw data in online repository). Specifically, we found 9 krill individuals (length <1 cm) in station d3: 2 in May, and 7 in April. However, general absence of sampled krill does not reflect their low occurrence in the field, as our sampling method was not suitable for krill. Further on, we only show results for copepods and nauplii. The body length of each animal was measured with ImageJ: the prosome length for copepods, and the length of the longest body axis (excluding antennae and cercal setae) for nauplii (Bottrell et al., 1976). Samples from the July sampling date were largely decomposed due to the very high biomass of zooplankton stored in flasks. Consequently, we cannot report size distribution for July samples, and we were only able to assess an approximate abundance of larger copepods (>1 mm; empty circles in Fig. 3C) by counting the connected packets of swimming legs, with one packet originating from one animal (Supporting information). These numbers underestimate the true zooplankton abundance, but were sufficient to identify the seasonal peak of copepod abundance, and are also valid when comparing abundances of copepods between sampling stations on that date.

We obtained the final zooplankton abundance values by multiplying the counted numbers by the subsampling factor (1 to 16). We calculated individual dry body weights using the length-to-weight relationships from Bottrell et al. (1976) for diverse species and life stages of copepods, which correspond well to weights of different stages of *Calanus finmarchicus* (Krause & Radach, 1993).

Whale sightings

Whale observation data were collected onboard three-hour whale watching tours operated by North Sailing and Gentle Giants by researchers and trained internship students from the

University of Iceland's Húsavík Research Centre. The tours were operating daily out of Húsavík (Skjálfandi Bay) between 4 April and 27 November 2024 (as described in Bertulli et al., 2018). Tours typically took place between 9:00 and 21:00, with at least two trips per day. The GPS track of the vessel and any whale sightings, including GPS location and species, were logged in the SpotterPro app (conserve.io). To provide an overview of baleen whale species presence, the number of "species positive" tours (blue whale (*Balaenoptera musculus*), humpback whale (*Megaptera novaeangliae*), and minke whale (*Balaenoptera acutorostrata*)) was divided by the total number of tours with observer coverage for each month (April-November). Of the total 690 recorded sightings, 90 were toothed whales including 48 white-beaked dolphins (*Lagenorhynchus albirostris*), 39 harbour porpoises (*Phocoena Phocoena*), and 3 killer whale (*Orcinus orca*) sightings. 591 baleen whale sightings included 508 humpback whales, 56 minke whales, and 26 blue whales (25 blue whales and one hybrid blue/fin whale). The sightings of a single sei whale and a single fin whale, were excluded from the baleen whale dataset, as well as four grey seals, one harbour seal, and three sightings marked as "unspecified".

Data analysis

The aim of our data analysis was to (1) test for significant drivers of food web components by running two complementary path analyses models, and (2) visualize and assess the phenology of the entire food web spanning different spatial and temporal scales.

Path analysis included in situ temperature, salinity, inorganic nutrients (P, N, and Si), chl_a (mg/m²), distance from shore, K_d, copepod abundance (non-naupliar individuals/m²), and monthly baleen whale sightings averaged over the entire bay. We included only sampling dates for which copepod data was available (n=12). All data were normalized using the standard score

prior to analyses. First, to find bottom-up drivers of food web dynamics, we performed a path analysis that included the following direct links: N, P and Si to chla; chla to copepods; and copepods to humpback, minke and blue whales. Second, to find significant environmental drivers of food web components, we included the following direct links in a new path analyses: Kd to chla; temperature to chla, copepods and humpback, minke and blue whales; salinity to chla, copepods and humpback, minke and blue whales; and distance from the shore to chla, copepods and humpback, minke and blue whales. Analyses were performed in R (version 2026.01.0) using “lme4” and “lavaan” packages. The raw data as well the R code used are available in the online repository (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20050257>).

Finally, to make an integrated phenological assessment of our data, we visualized the seasonal changes of: satellite-derived monthly average chla for the entire N Iceland region, in situ zooplankton abundance (station d3), and monthly occurrence of three baleen whale species averaged over the bay. We calculated monthly normalized response x_{norm} of all variables as follows: $x_{norm} = (x - x_{min}) / (x_{max} - x_{min})$, where x_{min} and x_{max} are minimum and maximum values, respectively, of each variable during the analyzed time period.

Results

Chlorophyll and water physico-chemistry

Chla derived from satellite data showed a bloom north of Iceland in May, followed by intermediate summer levels and a decline in September (Fig. 2). We found similar dynamics in situ: large increase in chla concentration in station d3 in May (up to ~80 mg/m²; Fig. 3B, Supporting information), followed by relatively high levels during summer in all marine stations,

and a second peak in station d3 and d5 in August (up to ~ 100 mg/m²; Fig. 3B, Supporting information). Chla concentration averaged over the entire region also showed the first, largest peak in late May (up to ~ 3.5 μ g/L; Supporting information), and a second peak in mid-August (up to ~ 2 μ g/L; Supporting information). Chla in the plumes was substantially lower than in marine stations, and peaked in August (up to ~ 35 mg/m² in laxplume; Fig. 3B, Supporting information).

Salinity, water temperature, light attenuation, and nutrient concentrations varied significantly between plume and marine stations and reflected strong spring freshwater influence from the rivers and seasonal changes (Supporting information). The lowest salinity (22) was measured in lax plume in May (after spring melt), while marine salinity was generally ~ 33 to 34, except for a low-salinity event at station d5 in May and July (lowest 25.8). Water temperature increased during spring (from April to May), to maximum ~ 8.9 to 9.8 °C in summer (July to August; Fig. 3B, Supporting information). Secchi depth at plume stations ranged from 11.5 m before melt and chla bloom (April) to 1.2 m after melt and during chla bloom (May), slightly increased in July, and dropped again in August (Supporting information). Marine stations had higher transparency in May (Secchi depth up to 12 m) that decreased in the following samplings (from 4.0 to 5.9 m in July, and 4.4 to 6.3 m in August). Si concentrations revealed strong river influence, with high concentrations in both rivers (>175 μ mol/L except for skj river on sampling 2), and plumes (minimum value 12.0 μ mol/L), that declined sharply offshore (maximum value station d5 4.6 μ mol/L) (Supporting information). In contrast, PO₄³⁻ and NO_x remained consistently low after April, except for a slight NO_x increase near plumes in July (up to 1.1 μ mol/L; Supporting information). Chla in the lax river increased from 0.9 μ g/L in April to 18.5 μ g/L in August,

whereas chl_a in the skj river remained low (0.3 to 0.6 µg/L), despite reaching the warmest temperature of 13.8 °C in July (Supporting information).

Zooplankton abundance and size structure

Copepod abundance remained low ($<10^4$ individuals/m²) in spring (April and May), reached its peak in July ($\sim 75\text{-}150 \times 10^3$ individuals/m²), and then declined in August ($\sim -20\%$ to -97%) (Fig. 3C). Thus, it largely tracked the seasonal dynamics of algal abundance measured both in the larger region (Fig. 2) as well as in situ (Fig. 3B, Supporting information): zooplankton abundance peaked in July after the first chl_a peak in May, and then decreased. The abundance of larval stages of copepods (nauplii) increased through the study period, with highest abundance in August (Fig. 3D). In general, more offshore areas were characterized by considerably higher copepod and naupliar abundances than the plume areas.

We found differences in the zooplankton community size structure and its seasonality between plume and marine stations (Fig. 4). In spring (April and May), all areas were dominated by smaller zooplankton (<1.5 mm; Fig. 4A, C, D). Dominance of larger zooplankton in the outer station d5 (>1.5 mm; Fig. 4F) is probably an artifact of the noted partial decomposition of animals in this sample, leading to absence of smaller individuals. Later in summer (August), lax plume station was still dominated by smaller zooplankton (2% of individuals >1.5 mm; Fig. 4B), whereas more offshore areas had a considerably higher proportion of larger individuals (11% and 19% of individuals >1.5 mm in stations d3 and d5, respectively; Fig. 4E, G). Moreover, the latter stations had a conspicuous bimodal distribution of body sizes, with one peak of small copepods and nauplii of around 0.4 mm length, and a second peak of larger, adult copepods of around 2.5 to 3 mm (Fig. 4E, G). The fraction of zooplankton smaller than 0.2 mm (the size used in the

monitoring program) was highest on 14 August in lax plume (3.8% as counted individuals, and 0.2% as estimated biomass), and lowest on 27 May in lax plume and d5 (0%) (Supporting information).

Baleen whale sightings

Sightings of humpback whales in the bay were frequent (248 trips with humpback whale sighted), mostly in central areas, and showed seasonal variation from April to November (Fig. 5, Supporting information). Sightings were absent in April, increased rapidly in May and remained high until October. By November, only a few sightings were recorded across the bay, although proportion of trips with sightings was still high. Humpback whales were nearly absent nearshore (Fig. 5). Sightings of minke whales were generally sparse (48 trips with minke whale sighted), with the highest number in April and August, and showed nearly opposite and less clear seasonality compared to humpbacks (Fig. 5, Supporting information). In April, minke sightings were concentrated near the southern and western coast, including the area of lax and skj plumes. Sightings during summer were widely dispersed across the bay, and dropped after August until 0 in November (Supporting information). Blue whale sightings were sparse (24 trips with blue whale sightings), and confined to April-June, with observations generally scattered throughout the bay (Figure 5C, Supporting information).

Food web interactions and phenology

Our first path analysis revealed positive bottom-up link between chl_a and copepods (Fig. 6A, Supporting information). Additionally, we found a negative link between Si and chl_a (probably because Si concentration, unlike chl_a, was the highest in the plumes) as well as between copepods and blue whales (probably due to absence of blue whales in summer when copepods

peak) (Fig. 6A, Supporting information). Interestingly, we found no significant effects of N and P on chl_a as well as positive, moderately strong but nonsignificant effect of copepods on humpback whales (Supporting information). The second path analysis clearly showed that distance from the shore and temperature are major abiotic drivers of the food web. Distance from the shore positively affected chl_a and copepods, and temperature positively affected copepods, humpback and blue whales (Fig. 6B, Supporting information).

An integrated phenology of the entire food web shows a clear pattern: chl_a peaked in May, followed by a rise in copepod abundance in July (no observations in June; Fig. 6C). Whales displayed sequential seasonal maxima: minke whale sightings peaked earliest in April and then again in August, blue whales in May before the copepod peak, and both copepods and humpback whales concurrently peaked in summer. However, the humpback whale occurrence stayed high from May to October while copepods declined after the July peak (Fig. 6C). The seasonality thus shows a progression from early presence of minke and blue whales, to the spring algae bloom to subsequent humpback and zooplankton increases. Minke whales remained in the bay the whole season.

Discussion

We investigated zooplankton abundance and size structure in Skjálfandi Bay during four surveys from April to August 2024, relating these patterns to water physico-chemistry, chl_a, and baleen whale sightings. Strong seasonal and spatial gradients characterized all variables. Silicon-rich freshwater inputs affected spring plume temperature, salinity, and light attenuation, while marine stations showed no river influence. Remarkably, we found persistently lower salinity and higher

chl_a at the outermost station. Chl_a peaked in late May, followed by a July peak in zooplankton abundance aligned with seasonal warming (Søreide et al., 2010). Nearshore *Calanus* communities (<7.5 km) consisted mostly of smaller individuals and had lower total abundance, whereas assemblages further offshore contained higher proportion of larger individuals and higher total abundance. Whale occurrence also varied seasonally: blue and minke whales appeared early, before the chlorophyll peak, with minke whales restricted to nearshore, while humpbacks peaked later, in mid-bay areas with high abundance of large *Calanus*. Distance from the shore and seasonally-driven temperature variation were the main drivers of food web dynamics, while chl_a positively influenced copepod abundance, with the latter and humpbacks displaying their seasonal highs in summer.

Our results show that, in contrast to the marine stations, the plume region was highly influenced by river inputs during spring (April-May), as reflected by water salinity, light attenuation, temperature, and chl_a. A clear freshwater and Si imprint from the rivers was evident in the bay, especially in spring, but dissolved inorganic nutrients (NO_x, PO₄³⁻) showed no strong river imprint and remained near depletion (~0.1 μM) throughout. Nutrient concentrations in the Laxá plume were higher than in the Skjálfandi plume, indicating that inputs from the Skjálfandi River supply only very little nutrients to the coast (Supporting information, Ólafsson, 1979). The marine stations lack the strong river signature. Low salinity and higher chl_a concentrations persist at the most outer station on both samplings in May and July, suggesting the occurrence of water fronts or local upwelling (Astthorsson et al., 2007; Devana et al., 2021; Gislason & Silva, 2012). Satellite-derived chl_a patterns as well as in situ chl_a concentrations showed a first peak in May, followed by another peak offshore in August (Supporting information), consistent with previous studies (Guðmundsson et al., 2009; McGinty et al., 2016).

Zooplankton abundance peak occurred in July (Fig. 2), which followed the phytoplankton spring bloom. This confirms strong bottom-up control of zooplankton populations by their algal resources (Astthorsson et al., 2007), as shown by the path analysis (Fig. 6A). We detected higher zooplankton abundance and biomass at outer stations than in plume areas, confirming our expectations and matching trends observed in the larger region (Astthorsson and Gislason, 1995; Gislason and Astthorsson, 2004). Nauplii also had strong seasonal dynamics, with low abundances throughout spring followed by a peak towards the end of summer (Fig. 2D), as a result of adult copepods reproducing around their abundance peak in July (Barth-Jensen et al., 2022; Daase et al., 2013). Both abundance and size structure of zooplankton communities differed along the spatial transect and across the season (Fig. 4). Smaller (< 1.5 mm) copepods, i.e., smaller species and/or younger stages, dominated all stations (Fig. 4). However, at the end of summer, Laxá plume showed yet more pronounced dominance of small individuals (Fig. 4B), whereas outer stations exhibited two distinct abundance peaks in size structure (Fig. 4E, G). This suggests that the *Calanus*-dominated communities follow a clear and synchronized phenology. Copepods typically overwinter as immature copepodite stages (Barth-Jensen et al., 2022; Heath et al., 2004), and reach maturity and adult size (around 2 to 3 mm) during a time window spanning early spring to summer in which they reproduce, subsequently producing an increasingly abundant cohort of small individuals. In our study area, this stage progression seems to be yet more synchronized, which could explain the near absence of zooplankton with a size between 1 and 2 mm in August (Fig. 4E, G). Additionally, we observed a marked decline in copepod abundance in August, particularly in the plume area (Fig. 3). This could have been caused by increased mortality (natural or predation-driven), or by migration to deeper, offshore water to prepare for the next overwintering period (Conover 1988, Hirche 1997). Such site-

specific zooplankton seasonal dynamics may affect energy transfer up the food web as well the burial of organic carbon from the surface to deeper ocean areas (Oziel et al., 2024). Our observation that smaller zooplankton individuals dominate nearshore (<25 km, but particularly <7.5 km from the coast) communities is particularly interesting as size structure of zooplankton and fish populations influences productivity at a large scale (Heneghan et al., 2023; Ratnarajah et al., 2023). (Sub)Arctic coastal regions are major contributors to global productivity, with an estimated 77% of the global fish capture linked to river processes (Gibson et al., 2022) that benefit fish especially at critical life stages (Gibson et al., 2022; Whitfield et al., 2023). These zones therefore represent functionally important habitats, and monitoring programs should include areas <7.5 and <25 km nearshore to capture whole-ecosystem dynamics.

A long-term dominance shift from minke to humpback whales was observed from 1995 to 2017 in the Skjálfandi Bay (Albrecht et al., 2021; Lechwar et al., 2023; Malinauskaite et al., 2022), and could be driven by reduced small fish availability close to the shore (Fayet et al. 2021), but could also reflect the overall decline of minke whales in Icelandic waters (Vikingsson et al, 2015). Additionally, sighting data were collected using the whale watching boats, which primarily targets humpback whales. Although we were not able to show a significant correlation between humpback whale occurrence and copepod abundance in Skjálfandi Bay, we may nevertheless draw some general conclusions about the local food web. Stable isotope analyses indicate that minke whales primarily consume small coastal fish such as sandeel (*Ammodytes* sp.), capelin, and herring (*Clupea harengus*) (Lechwar et al., 2023), whereas humpback whales feed mainly on krill (García-Vernet et al., 2021). Indeed, minke whales were confined to nearshore areas throughout the season, suggesting reliance on small fish that likely feed on smaller zooplankton. In contrast,

humpback whale feeding is related to high chl_a concentrations and areas with changes in temperature, depth, currents, and fronts, where prey can be found in high concentration (Meynecke et al., 2021). Accordingly, humpback whales coincided with zooplankton peak in summer, and were confined to the more outer stations with high *Calanus* abundance. This systematic presence of humpback whales in the bay as well as a positive (yet nonsignificant) correlation found between them and copepod abundance may be a sign of indirect reliance of humpbacks, via krill or small fish, on copepods as their food source (R. Hodgson, 2025; Savoca et al., 2021; Víkingsson et al., 2015).

Conclusions

Our results show that coastal areas form a dynamic and ecologically important niche within the marine ecosystem. We showed a clear seasonal pattern of the food web in Skjálfandi Bay: a peak in chlorophyll concentration in May followed by increased zooplankton abundance with a co-occurring peak in humpback whale sightings. Moreover, we found fine-scale differences in zooplankton structure across the sampled transect. Although all stations were within 25 km nearshore, and dominated by small (<1.5 mm) individuals, outer stations, with a more “marine” profile, are characterized by occurrence of larger (>1.5 mm) zooplankton and humpback presence. Areas closest to the shore (<7.5 km), on the other hand, harbor nearly only small (<1.5 mm) zooplankton that can fuel food webs all the way to their top consumers (specifically minke whales through small fish). Given ongoing climate warming, ocean surface freshening, altered currents across the Arctic Ocean, and shifts in sightings from minke to humpbacks in the bay, our results suggest that studying nearshore habitats is vital to understand the functioning of the broader ecosystem.

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(Note that high-resolution figures are available and can be provided upon manuscript acceptance or upon earlier request.)

Figure 1. (A) The study site located in north Iceland with five sampling stations, and the two main river inlets. (B) Picture of living *Calanus* zooplankton, and (C) Humpback whale feeding in Skjálfandi Bay, with a smaller river entering on the west side of the bay in the background, taken from a whale watching vessel.

Figure 2. Spatial and temporal distribution of monthly average chlorophyll-*a* concentration (derived from satellite images) in 2024 (one panel for each month; average concentrations in parentheses). Arrow points north, and Skjálfandi Bay is located in the black box.

Figure 3. Seasonal dynamics of sea surface temperature (A), in situ chlorophyll-*a* concentration (B), copepod abundance (C), and nauplius abundance (D) in lax plume (orange), skj plume (yellow), d3 (green), d4 (light blue) and d5 (dark blue) stations. Standard deviations for A and B are not shown for clarity (see instead Supporting information). Note that for July 10, only approximate abundance of copepods is shown (empty circles).

Figure 4. Size histograms of zooplankton communities on three sampling dates (rows) and in three sampling stations (columns). Shown are numbers of individuals in each size category, with size bin width 0.05 mm. Note that the May sample from d5 was of poor quality with smaller individuals potentially decomposed. Note different y-axis scale in each plot.

Figure 5. Distribution of opportunistic sightings in 2024 of humpback whales (A), minke whales (B), and blue whales (C). The number of individuals is indicated with a color scale, and the location indicates the location of the boat from which the whales were observed.

Figure 6. Path analysis results (A, B), and seasonal changes in chl a concentration, zooplankton abundance, and whale occurrence (normalized response $x = (x - x_{\min}) / (x_{\max} - x_{\min})$) (C).

In A and B, shown are significant ($p < 0.05$; black) and nearly significant correlations ($p < 0.065$; grey), and arrow thickness corresponds to link strengths (regression estimates). Shown are also +/- signs (positive or negative) of the estimates.

Sam-pling	Date (yyddmm)	Location	Distance from shore (m)	Chla (mg/m ²) (µg/L)	Salinity (PSU)	Tempe-rature (°C)	Secchi depth (m)	Kd (m ⁻¹)	PO ₄ ³⁻ (µmol/L)	NO _x (µmol/L)	Si (µmol/L)
1	240410	Lax river	-	0.9 ± 13%		NA			0.9 ± 6%	2.4 ± 2%	291.4 ± 3%
		Skj river	Partially frozen (inaccessible)								
	240419	Lax plume	25	3.6	31.8 ± 8%	3.2 ± 8%	11.5	0.15	0.8 ± 5%	10.1 ± 19%	30.4 ± 131%
d3		7500	38.8	34.3 ± 2%	5.8 ± 9%	10.5	0.16	0.8 ± 3%	10.3 ± 3%	13.3 ± 65%	
2	240531*	Lax river	-	2.7 ± 3%	-	12.9	-	-	0.5 ± 3%	0.2 ± 27%	233.7 ± 3%
		Skj river	-	0.38 ± 1%	-	12.3	-	-	0.3 ± 2%	0.3 ± 34%	35.2 ± 20%
	240527	Lax plume	25	11.2	22.0 ± 39%	8.4 ± 26%	1.2	1.42	0.1 ± 68%	0.2 ± 81%	35.9 ± 135%
		d3	7500	77.6	34.3 ± 4%	5.8 ± 13%	10.5	0.16	0.1 ± 48%	0.5 ± 48%	2.8 ± 43%
		d5	25000	91.9	33.3 ± 8%	6.4 ± 14%	12.0	0.14	0.1 ± 76%	0.2 ± 120%	1.7 ± 45%
3	240708	Lax river	-	1.2 ± 1%	-	13.1	-	-	0.4 ± 1%	0.2 ± 20%	204.2 ± 1%
		Skj river	-	0.6 ± 1%	-	13.8	-	-	0.6 ± 9%	0.2 ± 18%	175.5 ± 44%
	240710	Lax Plume	25	35.8	32.1 ± 8%	9.6 ± 12%	5.1	0.33	0.3 ± 126%	1.1 ± 128%	15.4 ± 92%
		Skj plume	25	17.5	33.9 ± 6%	9.6 ± 17%	5.7	0.30	0.1 ± 39%	0.4 ± 142%	12.0 ± 72%
		d3	7500	61.4	33.0 ± 8%	8.9 ± 22%	4.0	0.43	0.1 ± 50%	0.1 ± 103%	16.0 ± 91%
		d4	13000	75.0	32.3 ± 14%	9.8 ± 12%	5.5	0.31	0.1 ± 95%	0.2 ± 98%	6.2 ± 53%
d5	25000	85.1	25.8 ± 30%	9.7 ± 7%	5.9	0.29	0.1 ± 61%	0.1 ± 81%	4.6 ± 92%		
4	240825	Lax river	-	18.5 ± 4.7%	-	7.1	-	-	0.1 ± 9%	0.2 ± 17%	179.5 ± 5%
		Skj river	-	0.3 ± 1%	-	5.9	-	-	0.7 ± 12%	0.2 ± 15%	208.5 ± 28%
	240827	Lax plume	25	17.0	32.1 ± 16%	8.9 ± 15%	3.2	0.53	0.1 ± 85%	0.1 ± 66%	14.6 ± 156%
		d3	7500	85.5	32.7 ± 12%	8.9 ± 12%	4.4	0.39	0.1 ± 35%	0.1 ± 48%	4.7 ± 136%
d5	25000	106.7	31.8 ± 16%	8.4 ± 7%	6.3	0.27	0.1 ± 62%	0.1 ± 62%	3.2 ± 40%		

Table S1. Average ± SD (in percent) chlorophyll-*a* concentrations and water physico-chemical parameters, averaged from 1m, 5m, and 10m depth (and integrated over up to 50 m for chla), and of lax and skj rivers. For the rivers (in blue), one temperature measurement is taken and triplicate chla measurements.

*River temperature data is from 240614 instead of 240531.

Month	Total trips	Humpback whale	Minke whale	Blue whale
April	45	0.07	0.24	0.09
May	48	0.96	0.10	0.33
June	38	0.89	0.16	0.11
July	50	0.98	0.12	0.00
August	38	0.92	0.29	0.00
September	36	0.89	0.17	0.00
October	37	1.00	0.08	0.00
November	17	0.71	0.00	0.00

Table S2. Total trips (including trips with no sighting) and number of sightings per trip of humpback, minke and blue whales in the bay in 2024.

Link	Estimate	Standard error	z-value	p-value
Chlorophyll ~ Nitrogen	0.78	0.84	0.93	0.36
Chlorophyll ~ Phosphorus	-0.96	0.86	-1.12	0.26
Chlorophyll ~ Silicate	-0.66	0.20	-3.35	0.00
Copepods ~ Chlorophyll	0.47	0.26	1.85	0.06
Humpback ~ Copepods	0.26	0.28	0.94	0.35
Minke ~ Copepods	0.10	0.29	0.35	0.73
Blue ~ Copepods	-0.53	0.24	-2.18	0.03

Table S3. The results of a path analysis model with direct bottom-up trophic links between nitrogen, phosphorus, silicate, chlorophyll, copepods, and whales (humpback, minke, blue). The links are represented as $A \sim B$, meaning that B has an effect on A (i.e., A depends on B). Significant effects ($p < 0.05$) are shown in bold.

Link	Estimate	Standard error	z-value	p-value
Chlorophyll ~ Temperature	0.12	0.14	0.87	0.39
Chlorophyll ~ Salinity	0.35	0.26	1.35	0.18
Chlorophyll ~ Kd	0.09	0.27	0.34	0.73
Chlorophyll ~ Distance	0.92	0.18	5.09	0.00
Copepods ~ Salinity	-0.06	0.23	-0.27	0.79
Copepods ~ Temperature	0.46	0.23	2.05	0.04
Copepods ~ Distance	0.51	0.21	2.40	0.02
Humpback ~ Salinity	0.01	0.18	0.07	0.94
Humpback ~ Temperature	0.81	0.18	4.52	0.00
Humpback ~ Distance	0.13	0.17	0.77	0.44
Minke ~ Salinity	0.22	0.30	0.75	0.45
Minke ~ Temperature	-0.07	0.30	-0.22	0.82
Minke ~ Distance	0.02	0.28	0.08	0.94
Blue ~ Salinity	-0.44	0.23	-1.89	0.06
Blue ~ Temperature	-0.65	0.23	-2.81	0.01
Blue ~ Distance	-0.02	0.22	-0.08	0.93

Table S4. The results of a path analysis model with direct links between environmental variables (temperature, salinity, distance from the shore, Kd) and food web components (chlorophyll, copepods, humpback whales, minke whales, blue whales). The links are represented as $A \sim B$, meaning that B has an effect on A (i.e., A depends on B). Significant effects ($p < 0.05$) are shown in bold.

Fig. S1. Example of a packet of swimming legs of a single copepod individual, used to estimate the abundance of copepods on the third (10 July) sampling date. Note that, with this method, only leg packets of larger (>1.5 mm) copepods are identifiable.

Fig. S2. Seasonal dynamics of salinity (averaged over the upper 10 m depth; A), the Secchi depth (B), and nutrient concentration (PO_4^{3-} , NO_x and Si, averaged over the upper 10 m depth; C, D, E). Standard deviations for salinity and nutrients are not shown for clarity (see instead Table S1).

Fig. S3. Chlorophyll-*a* concentrations in 2024 averaged per day over the entire Northern Iceland region (as in Fig. 2), including the Skjálfandi Bay.

Fig. S4. Seasonal dynamics of copepod (A) and nauplius (B) abundance shown per unit volume (m^3), and total biomass (copepods and nauplius together) shown per unit surface (m^2 , C) and per unit volume (m^3 , D); in lax plume (orange), skj plume (yellow), d3 (green), d4 (light blue) and d5 (dark blue) stations. Note that for July 10, only approximate abundance of copepods is shown (empty circles).

Individual biomass has been estimated using the length-to-weight conversion formula of Bottrell et al. (1976):

$$\ln W = 1.9526 + 2.399 \cdot \ln L$$

where W is dry weight in μg , and L is body length in mm (the prosome length for copepods, and the length of the longest body axis excluding antennae and cercal setae for nauplii).

Fig. S5. Weight histograms of zooplankton communities on three sampling dates (rows) and at three sampling stations (columns). Shown are numbers of individuals in each size category, with size bin width $2.5 \mu\text{g}$. Animals heavier than $200 \mu\text{g}$ (12 individuals in total) have been removed for clarity. Note different y-axis scale in each plot.